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Реінтеграція тимчасово окупованих територій України на засадах сталого розвитку

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Анотація: Стаття спрямована на всебічний аналіз процесу реінтеграції тимчасово окупованих територій України через призму Цілей сталого розвитку ООН. Дослідження має на меті визначити ключові бар'єри, можливості та пріоритети політики відновлення для територій із різним рівнем руйнувань та різною глибиною окупації.

Використано міждисциплінарний підхід, що включає PESTEL-аналіз, порівняння сценаріїв деокупації, оцінку потенціалу соціально-економічного відновлення та аналіз відповідності локальних потреб пріоритетним ЦСР. Застосування кейс-аналізу щодо Бахмута, Мелітополя та Севастополя дозволило виділити структурні відмінності у викликах та можливостях.

Встановлено, що реінтеграція потребує поєднання базового відновлення критичної інфраструктури з довгостроковими стратегіями сталого розвитку. Визначено групу ключових Цілей – 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 16 та 17 – які формують основу для планування політик на місцевому рівні. Для кожного міста визначено пріоритети: для Бахмута – повне відтворення та «зелене» відновлення; для Мелітополя – модернізація агросектору та критичної інфраструктури; для Севастополя – політична трансформація, переорієнтація економіки та вирішення системних екологічних проблем.

Реінтеграція можлива лише за умови комплексного бачення, що поєднує інституційну стійкість, інноваційні моделі відновлення та широку міжнародну підтримку. Реалізація ЦСР виступає ключовим інструментом для формування довгострокової політики трансформації та відновлення соціальної довіри. Дослідження підкреслює необхідність створення єдиного органу державного управління, формування кадрового резерву та залучення міжнародних партнерів.

Ключові слова: менеджмент, управління, реінтеграція, сталий розвиток, відновлення, постконфліктний розвиток, PESTEL-аналіз.

**Reintegration of temporarily occupied territories of Ukraine based on
sustainability**

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Abstract: Purpose. This article examines the reintegration of Ukraine's temporarily occupied territories through the framework of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The study aims to identify barriers, opportunities, and priority directions for rebuilding territories with different levels of destruction and various depths of occupation. It focuses on Occupied Territories, that address multifaceted issues, focusing on policies for IDPs, humanitarian assistance, and restoration efforts.

Methods. The research applies an interdisciplinary methodology, integrating PESTEL analysis, scenario-based assessment of de-occupation, evaluation of socio-economic recovery potential, and alignment with priority SDGs. A case-based comparison of Bakhmut, Melitopol, and Sevastopol highlights structural differences in development prospects.

Results. Findings demonstrate that reintegration requires combining urgent restoration of critical infrastructure with long-term sustainable development strategies. A cluster of essential SDGs – 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 16, and 17 – forms the basis for local recovery planning. City-specific priorities were identified: Bakhmut requires complete reconstruction and green redevelopment; Melitopol needs modernization of the agro-industrial base and critical infrastructure; Sevastopol faces the most complex political, social, and environmental transformation, including economic reorientation and addressing systemic water scarcity.

Conclusions. Reintegration is feasible only through a multi-vector strategy grounded in institutional resilience, inclusive governance, innovative recovery models, and strong international partnerships. The SDGs serve as a strategic framework for post-conflict transformation and rebuilding social cohesion. The study also emphasizes the need for a unified state reintegration authority and a strengthened human-capital base.

Keywords: management, governance, reintegration, sustainable development, recovery, post-conflict transformation, PESTEL analysis.

Topic rationale. The reintegration of temporarily occupied territories in Ukraine, particularly in the context of achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), presents a complex and pressing challenge rooted in the geopolitical conflict that escalated in 2014. Following the annexation of Crimea and ongoing hostilities in Eastern Ukraine, the country faces severe socio-economic disruptions, with over 13,000 fatalities and approximately 1.4 million internally displaced persons (IDPs) resulting from the conflict [1,2]. The Ministry for Reintegration of Temporarily Occupied Territories was established to address these multifaceted issues, focusing on policies for IDPs, humanitarian assistance, and restoration efforts. However, discussions about restructuring this ministry reflect ongoing administrative challenges in effectively managing the reintegration process amidst the war's destructive consequences [3]. The SDGs offer a framework to guide

Ukraine's recovery and development efforts by promoting economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental sustainability. In collaboration with international organizations, Ukraine's government is working to integrate these goals into national policies and local planning through initiatives such as the Open SDGs Platform, which enhances transparency and tracks progress in achieving specific targets [4,5]. However, achieving these goals remains hindered by fragmented strategic planning, insufficient funding, and the war's ongoing socio-economic impacts, leading to infrastructure, health care, and community cohesion challenges [6].

Notably, implementing SDGs in post-conflict settings like Ukraine reveals both opportunities and significant barriers. The socio-economic toll of the conflict exacerbates poverty and inequality, complicating efforts to address urgent needs while fostering long-term development. Moreover, the interaction between local initiatives and international support highlights the necessity of inclusive governance and community participation to ensure that recovery efforts meet the needs of affected populations, thereby reinforcing social cohesion and stability [7,8].

The path forward is fraught with complexities, particularly as ongoing violence continues to undermine the reintegration of affected territories and populations. The interconnectedness of local and global challenges necessitates a coordinated approach to sustainable development in Ukraine, emphasizing resilience and collaboration among civil society, governmental bodies, and international partners [9,10]. As the country navigates these tumultuous waters, the pursuit of the SDGs serves as a vital beacon for guiding recovery and fostering a sustainable future.

Literature review. The conflict in Ukraine has its roots in a series of geopolitical tensions, beginning with the attempted annexation of Crimea and armed aggression in Eastern Ukraine in 2014. This aggressive action has significantly endangered peace, security, and cooperation in Eastern Europe, resulting in considerable human losses, estimated at over 13,000, and substantial economic damage, which has led to a large-scale internal displacement of approximately 1.4 million people. The destructive consequences of this armed conflict have posed

extreme challenges, resolving issues related to the reintegration of temporarily occupied territories (TOT) a pressing concern for Ukraine. In response to the ongoing conflict, the Ministry for Reintegration of Temporarily Occupied Territories of Ukraine (MinReintegration) was established with a wide range of responsibilities to address the negative consequences of war. These responsibilities include forming and implementing state policy concerning internally displaced persons (IDPs) and those who have fled abroad due to the conflict, as well as coordinating humanitarian assistance and restoring peace. However, recent governmental reshuffles have led to discussions about merging the MinReintegration with the Ministry for Communities, Territories, and Infrastructure of Ukraine, indicating a shift in the administrative approach to addressing these complex issues. Achieving sustainable development in post-conflict Ukraine necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the challenges posed by the conflict, particularly regarding social cohesion and the reintegration of displaced populations. This includes a need for a coordinated effort to assess ongoing initiatives, identify gaps, and recognize the long-term impacts on various sectors, such as environmental and economic sustainability [11]. The conflict's geographic scale has led to widespread damage to ecosystems, especially in Ukraine's southern and eastern steppe regions, further complicating the path to sustainable development [1]. Moreover, the global context has evolved, with increased conflict severity and duration influencing the progress toward the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This highlights the interconnected nature of local and global challenges, where international cooperation and effective governance are vital for achieving peace and resilience in the face of adversity. Thus, the historical context of Ukraine's ongoing conflict is crucial for understanding the complexities of reintegration efforts and the broader goal of achieving the SDGs.

Modern Context of Implementation of SDGs in Ukraine. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in Ukraine represent a comprehensive framework aimed at fostering economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental sustainability while addressing the unique challenges faced by the country. The Government of Ukraine, in

collaboration with international partners such as the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), has established various initiatives to facilitate the integration of the SDGs into national and local planning.

The concept of “reintegration of temporarily occupied territories” in the work of Selikhov D. S. [12] is revealed through an analysis of its key legal characteristics, structural elements, and functional purpose within state policy. The study substantiates the need to formalize legal procedures that ensure the restoration of state sovereignty, security, and public administration in de-occupied territories.

Theoretical and legal approaches to the reintegration of occupied and annexed territories in the publication by Medyanyk I. S. [13] are presented through a comparison of Ukrainian and international models of political and legal restoration. The focus is placed on institutional and normative challenges that complicate the process of regaining control over territories, as well as on the conceptual foundations for developing an effective reintegration strategy.

The legal foundations of reintegration policy for temporarily occupied territories in the research of Minakova Ye. V. [14] are examined through an analysis of mechanisms for restoring public administration, security, and legal order. The author also identifies gaps in current legislation and emphasizes the need for its modernization to ensure the effective return of territories and populations to Ukraine’s legal system.

Conceptual problems of forming state policy on temporarily occupied territories in the work of Shaptala N. K. and Kaminska N. V. [15] are described through the identification of fragmented scientific approaches and contradictions in the existing discourse. The researchers highlight the importance of integrating humanitarian, legal, and security components in order to develop an effective system of public governance during reintegration.

The pathways to de-occupation and subsequent reintegration of territories in the publication by Skobelska O. R. [16] are examined through an emphasis on restoring public trust and overcoming the consequences of propaganda and prolonged information influence. The author stresses the importance of comprehensive

humanitarian, legal, and security measures, as well as the role of communication strategies and community participation.

The set of indicators for evaluating the outcomes of territorial recovery in the study by Martynovych N. O. [17] is presented through a systematic approach to assessing the socio-economic effectiveness of reconstruction. The proposed framework includes infrastructural, demographic, economic, and administrative indicators, forming a basis for high-quality evaluation of recovery progress.

The analysis of regional fragility in Ukraine in the work of Vdovyn M. Ya. and Dmytrenko Kh. [18] is conducted through the identification of key social, economic, and environmental factors determining regional resilience. The study proposes methods for assessing vulnerability and indicators to guide decision-making in the context of post-war recovery and reintegration.

Foreign experience in developing reintegration models for territories that have undergone occupation or annexation in the study by Medyanyk I. [19] is presented through an analysis of transitional justice instruments, institutional restoration, and security mechanisms. The article demonstrates how practices from the Balkans, Georgia, and Cyprus can be adapted to the Ukrainian context, taking into account legal, social, and administrative factors.

In 2025, Ukraine continues to integrate sustainable development principles, particularly by implementing the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS). This involves the introduction of regulations on the preparation, submission and publication of sustainability reporting for large enterprises. Ukraine also continues to work on achieving the 17 Sustainable Development Goals defined by the UN, which include poverty eradication, decent work, environmental protection and others (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Key aspects of sustainable development in Ukraine in 2025

Source: [4; 20; 21]

Identification of previously unresolved aspects of the general problem

Previous research on the reintegration of temporarily occupied territories has largely focused on legal and security issues, while the managerial dimension through the lens of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) remains insufficiently explored. The practical mechanisms for applying the SDGs to territories with varying levels of destruction, duration of occupation, and demographic shifts are still unclear.

Existing studies lack a typology of temporarily occupied territories and corresponding sustainable development priorities, as well as tools that integrate PESTEL analysis with SDG implementation at the local level. Governance models that would account for different de-occupation scenarios and ensure effective coordination between central authorities, local governments, and international partners are not adequately developed.

Institutional mechanisms, staffing capacities, and the ability to introduce green and inclusive recovery models under resource constraints also remain underexamined. Further research should focus on differentiated SDG application, integration of the

PESTEL framework into strategic planning, and the creation of effective management models for reintegration.

Formulation of the Article's Objectives (Problem Statement)

The purpose of the article is to substantiate approaches to the reintegration of Ukraine's temporarily occupied territories based on the principles of sustainable development, using the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as a framework for shaping recovery policies.

To achieve this purpose, the following objectives are set:

1. Summarize theoretical and legal approaches to reintegration in the context of sustainable development.
2. Identify the specific features of applying the SDGs to the recovery of territories with different levels of destruction and varying durations of occupation.
3. Synthesize the results of the PESTEL analysis for three types of territories and determine the corresponding sustainable development priorities.
4. Outline differences in reintegration challenges and opportunities using the cases of Bakhmut, Melitopol, and Sevastopol.
5. Formulate managerial guidelines and conditions for the effective implementation of reintegration policy based on the SDGs.

Main part. During the reintegration of the TOT of Ukraine, there is a temptation to find simple solutions to rather complex problems and decisions, among which the security sector and basic social security should become the main and only priorities, while other aspects of socio-economic growth and care for future generations should recede into the background, wait for "better circumstances" and "opportunities." Let us try to explain why we should take care in advance of a comprehensive approach to the sustainable development of territories that will require special care and expertise in management decisions. The first thesis is that the territory will have the potential for development and post-war recovery when it is attractive for permanent residence of the population and investments. It is about preventing demographic distortions, creating prospects for young people, creating sustainable and attractive jobs, and creating career

growth opportunities based on innovations in any field of activity. The second thesis is that security should be considered comprehensively. It is not only about clearing the territory from explosive objects and other remnants of war but also about compliance with the requirements of environmental safety, which should be ensured by sustainable nature management, prevention of environmental pollution, regulation of waste management, preservation of biodiversity and "green" management technologies. Among the Sustainable Development Goals, the ones closest to post-war recovery are: Clean water and adequate sanitation, Affordable and clean energy, Decent work and economic growth, Industry, innovation and infrastructure, Sustainable development of cities and communities. Let us consider these goals and their prospects for project implementation under two basic scenarios of de-occupation - diplomatic and military.

For example, let's take three cities that have experienced occupation differently and have other basic conditions for organizing the city economy and social sphere. Our considerations are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1.

Implementation of Sustainable Development Goals for different conditions of de-occupation within the cities of Ukraine

SDG Goal	Bakhmut	Melitopol	Sevastopol (Aqyar)
Clean Water and Sanitation	Absence of water supply and sewage systems	Outdated water supply and sewage infrastructure, population decline, shortage of qualified personnel	Increasing urban population (water consumers), outdated water purification and sewage systems, discharge of polluted wastewater into the sea
Affordable and Clean Energy	Decommissioning of power grid infrastructure creates potential for renewable energy development.	Electricity generation from Russian territory will be unavailable, and generation from Ukrainian territory will be limited due to the Zaporizhzhia NPP shutdown; the city may face electricity shortages.	Potential energy deficit due to the inability to promptly reorient power supply from mainland Ukraine

SDG Goal	Bakhmut	Melitopol	Sevastopol (Aqyar)
Decent Work and Economic Growth	Labor potential will be restored through the city's function as a "near rear," so economic growth will be closely tied to the security situation	Labor potential has significantly changed due to the outflow of skilled workers and an increasing elderly population.	A significant portion of the workforce is integrated into the Russian sociocultural space and may leave with the withdrawal of Russian armed forces.
Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	Industrial recovery must rely solely on available human resources and security-related objectives	Development of processing and food industries will depend on agricultural progress in southern Ukraine; investment attractiveness will depend on available workforce and infrastructure	Industrial growth will depend on the ability to repurpose the military-oriented economy to serve Ukraine's defense sector, or to shift industrial specialization entirely
Sustainable Cities and Communities	The city's reconstruction offers an opportunity to embed SDG priorities in its strategic development planning.	Sustainable urban development will be constrained by a challenging demographic situation, where social welfare needs will take priority and become a burden on the local economy.	The sustainable development strategy must account for the existing population and the need to preserve key urban functions (fleet maintenance, services, repairs, etc.), making SDG integration highly dependent on the nature of de-occupation

Source: developed by authors

The features of reintegration are a balanced combination of the most relevant for the first steps of reintegration of Sustainable Development Goals and their adaptation to rapidly changing conditions. For example, Bakhmut may not choose its own strategy for the relevant development model until February 2022, but concentrate on its capabilities for rebuilding the city in other areas: the security function and its implementation as a "near rear" function. Bakhmut has the opportunity to rebuild from a "clean slate," that is, to lay the most effective urban planning solutions and development strategies at the urban planning level. Among the SD Goals, "Sustainable

development of cities and communities" will be important for Bakhmut because, during the period of determining the priorities of recovery, it is the ideas of sustainable interactions and goals of harmonious functioning that will come to the fore in urban space planning.

Melitopol, as a city that has retained more than half of its pre-war population, has a somewhat skewed sex-age structure, with an increasing proportion of the elderly and the need for labor migration, especially to ensure the normal functioning of critical infrastructure. The current state of critical infrastructure actually corresponds to the level of 2022. The city's critical infrastructure is almost entirely dependent on energy supply, available qualified personnel for its maintenance, and support for housing and communal services. Therefore, among the factors for implementing the SR Goals will be the preservation of the minimum necessary card potential of the city economy and support for its activities. The implementation of the SR Goal "Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure" will depend on the strategic vision of the industrial complex, which will be appropriate for development in Melitopol. Traditionally, the city specialized in servicing the agro-industrial complex, repairing and producing agricultural products food products, and processing of raw materials. However, the sex-age structure of the city has undergone significant changes. The proportion of the population of retirement age has increased significantly due to the reduction in production after 2022, the number of qualified specialists has significantly decreased, and no institution of higher and secondary specialized education is left in the city. This means that the development of industry will be limited by: human resources energy deficit (Zaporizhzhia NPP is currently in a state of "cold shutdown," and the restoration of its operation will require several years because it is no coincidence that the occupation authorities are still unable to launch the nuclear power plant for normal operation).

Sevastopol (Akyar) is a city with preserved infrastructure and main branches of Industry and urban economy. The goals of the SR should take into account the political and social potential of the city, its adaptability to the requirements of the external environment and internal human potential. The features of the implementation of the

Goals of the SR are: achieving civil consensus, coordination and effectiveness of local policy, targeted financing of measures that contribute to approaching the identified priorities of sustainable development. For Sevastopol, within the Goal "Clean Water and Adequate Sanitation" framework, the most relevant are: solving waste management problems (a waste processing plant was not built until 2014 and the occupation authorities did not build it either). The second component of this problem is clean drinking water. The Chornorichny reservoir is filled exclusively with natural runoff, which has been decreasing for almost 20 years (in practice, the dehydration of the rivers of Crimea has been observed since the 2010s; however, the most dramatic reductions in runoff volumes occurred during the period of the annexation of the peninsula, in particular, in 2019-2021, in the future the situation remains difficult, the water content of artificial reservoirs of Crimea does not, in general, meet the needs for water supply). It is appropriate to note here that the main rivers of Crimea – Alma, Belbek, Kokozka, and Chorna – are increasingly losing their riverbed water content altogether. Thus, the river Alma, on average, has been in a "dry channel" state for 144 days a year over the past 4 years of observation. Sevastopol has not yet had significant problems with water supply, solely due to political and administrative factors. The top military leadership of Crimea, the Russian security services in Crimea, and part of the political leadership are located there. Therefore, the city has no problems with water supply, unlike, for example, the administrative center of the peninsula, the city of Simferopol (Akmestzhit). Crimea, as a whole, has a problem with a sustainable electricity supply. Crimea's electricity networks during the annexation will be tied to the Russian power system, which stretches from the Krasnodar Territory of Russia through the Kerch Strait and along the coast of the Sea of Azov, so when the peninsula is de-occupied, there may be a shortage of electricity, which should be partially compensated for by the active construction of solar and wind power plants. Before the annexation, construction of large solar power plants began in Crimea (in particular, West Crimea), but after the annexation, all these projects were suspended or liquidated.

Implementing the goal "Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure" for Sevastopol will have certain features. The city has built a military model of the economy, and enterprises were focused on the repair of military equipment, in particular, vessels of the Russian naval forces. In addition, some of the production actually works in the Russian military-industrial complex, which will cause certain complications with their re-profiling or specialization after de-occupation.

PESTEL analysis: Reintegration of Ukraine's TOT in the context of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The process of reintegration of temporarily occupied territories of Ukraine is an extremely complex and multidimensional challenge, encompassing political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal aspects. In the post-war period, this process cannot be reduced to the restoration of control over the territories alone, but should include a long-term vision of sustainable development, the formation of inclusive institutions, modernization of infrastructure, as well as the elimination of deep social, demographic and value gaps. Accordingly, the integration of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into reintegration policies is not only desirable, but also a critically necessary prerequisite for the successful transformation of the post-occupation landscape.

In this context, the PESTEL analysis (table 2) allows us to identify key external factors that will affect the possibilities of implementing the SDGs in three types of territories: deeply annexed (Sevastopol), recently occupied (Melitopol), and destroyed as a result of hostilities (Bakhmut). Further, based on the assessment of challenges and potentials under individual SDGs, a priority matrix was developed, which allows for a structured identification of which development areas are of primary importance in each type of territory. This provides a basis for the targeted formulation of reintegration strategies adapted to the local context, constraints and resources.

Table 2.

PESTEL analysis

Component of analysis	Sevastopol	Melitopol	Bakhmut
Political	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deep integration into the Russian administrative space. - Powerful Russian military presence and propaganda. - There is a need for complex political transformation and demilitarization. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The political structure is partly imported from the Russian Federation, but not yet deeply rooted. - Lack of legitimate local self-government. - Higher probability of acceptance of Ukrainian power with proper communication. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complete absence of local self-government. - Significant destruction of political institutions. - The need for institutional development "from scratch".
Economical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Focus on the Russian military-industrial complex. - Investment restrictions due to sanctions. - Difficult incorporation into the Ukrainian economy without restructuring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The agro-sector is a key industry. - Loss of connections with the logistics centers of Ukraine. - Potential for renewable energy and processing. - Vulnerable employment and migration of personnel 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complete destruction of the economy. - Possibilities for building a "green" recovery. - The need for donor funding for any economic activity
Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The identity of part of the population gravitates towards the Russian Federation. - A long-term program of readaptation, work with trauma, and de-occupational education is needed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Part of the population has retained loyalty to Ukraine. - Social structures have not been destroyed. - High demand for medical and psychosocial assistance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forced displacement of the majority of the population. - High level of trauma (psychological and physical). - Social fabric needs reconstruction from scratch
Technological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Outdated infrastructure. - Difficulty in implementing Ukrainian technical standards. - Ensuring cybersecurity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partial destruction of technical systems. - The need for modernization of water supply, energy. - Prospects for innovative models of the "green" economy 	

Component of analysis	Sevastopol	Melitopol	Bakhmut
Environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Problems with water supply and wastewater treatment. - Discharges into the sea, degradation of the Black Sea coast. - Pollution from military bases. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Soil depletion, water problems, destruction of agricultural ecosystems. - Need for land restoration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total ecological disaster (soil, rivers, forests). - There is a need for an ecological audit and reclamation.
Law	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a need for a complete legal revision of all institutions (from education to the judicial system). - Integration into the legal field of Ukraine is complex. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a need to implement Ukrainian law and hold the occupation administration accountable. - More space for peaceful legal transformation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complete lack of law and order. - Need for transitional justice, lustration, amnesty, etc.

Source: developed by authors

To sum up a study based on several possible cases (Table 2) .

(1) Sevastopol is the most complex reintegration case, requiring political transformation and deep readaptation of society. The economy is oriented towards the Russian Federation, and the environmental risks are systemic.

(2) Melitopol has greater potential for inclusive recovery, given its high dependence on the infrastructure of southern Ukraine and the agricultural sector. It is important to restore humanitarian trust here quickly.

(3) Bakhmut is a case of "rebuilding from scratch" that can become a pilot recovery model under the SDGs, emphasizing a green economy, inclusive infrastructure, and community participation.

In the process of reintegration of the temporarily occupied territories of Ukraine, one of the most important challenges is to build an effective, systematic and long-term development strategy that takes into account not only the immediate needs of recovery, but also ensuring a sustainable peaceful future. In this context, the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as a global reference point, provide a meaningful

framework for assessing challenges and building policies at the local level. However, taking into account the scale of destruction, the different duration and depth of occupation, demographic changes, destroyed infrastructure and the specifics of each territory, five key goals were selected from among the 17 SDGs, which are critically important at the stage of reintegration.

Goal 6: Clean water and adequate sanitation. In the temporarily occupied territories, acute problems with access to high-quality drinking water, sanitation, and sanitation are noted. Many networks are destroyed or worn out, and in a number of regions (in particular, the southern regions) they did not meet the needs of the population even before the start of full-scale war. Given the threats to public health, ecology and sustainable recovery, this goal is one of the basic ones.

Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy. Energy independence and reliable electricity supply are the basis for the viability of territories. After de-occupation, a number of regions may remain disconnected from centralized energy sources, especially if previous energy solutions were technically or politically linked to the aggressor. Promoting renewable energy projects, microgrids, and energy-efficient solutions can act not only as an infrastructure but also as an economic strategy.

Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth. The labor potential of the de-occupied territories has suffered both due to the physical emigration of the population and the degradation of economic infrastructure. In addition to the outflow of skilled personnel, part of the population has ended up in the shadow or military sector. Ensuring decent work is a guarantee of social stability, overcoming poverty and restoring trust in the state.

Goal 9: Industrialization, innovation and infrastructure. This goal directly concerns material recovery - modernization of industry, transport infrastructure, logistics, digital networks. At the same time, it opens up the opportunity for an innovative approach to post-war development, including new specializations for regions (for example, defense or "green" economy clusters).

Goal 10: Reduced Inequalities. The reintegration of temporarily occupied territories requires a systematic redress of socio-economic, political and legal inequalities resulting from prolonged occupation. Residents of such territories may have different levels of access to health, education, administrative services, and limited legal protection. Reducing inequalities between these regions and the rest of Ukraine is a critical element of successful reintegration. This also includes overcoming discrimination and integrating vulnerable groups, including IDPs, persons with disabilities, ethnic minorities, and veterans.

Goal 11: Sustainable development of cities and communities. Destroyed cities require not only physical reconstruction, but also a new vision of spatial development, provision of housing for IDPs, inclusiveness, community participation in planning. The development strategy must comply with the principles of barrier-free, environmental friendliness, social integration - and it is this Goal that provides the necessary framework for such transformations.

Goal 12: Responsible Consumption and Production. In the context of rebuilding infrastructure and industry in de-occupied territories, it is important not to repeat the wrong models of environmentally harmful production. Reintegration opens a window of opportunity for the implementation of the principles of the circular economy, environmentally responsible waste management, green procurement, and energy-efficient technologies. Responsible consumption and production also contribute to long-term sustainability and business responsibility, which is the basis of sustainable development.

Goal 13: Climate Action. The occupied territories have suffered large-scale environmental and climate impacts: destruction of green areas, disruption of water balance, soil degradation, man-made pollution. Their restoration must take into account climate risks and adaptation approaches. In addition, reintegration allows for the implementation of climate-oriented planning - for example, green infrastructure, alternative energy, water conservation, etc. Taking into account SDG 13 is a condition for the formation of resilient ecosystems in the post-conflict period.

Goal 16: Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions. SDG 16 is fundamental in the context of post-conflict settlement and reintegration. It covers tasks such as restoring trust in institutions, ensuring fair justice, investigating war crimes, integrating the local population into the legal system of Ukraine and ensuring their participation in decision-making. Building strong institutions, transparency, and the rule of law will be key to preventing re-escalation.

Goal 17: Partnerships for the Goals. Effective reintegration requires broad engagement by the international community, donors, the UN, civil society, local authorities, business and academia. Implementing large-scale change in de-occupied territories requires intersectoral partnerships, funding, expertise, and knowledge sharing. SDG 17 emphasizes the importance of a systematic and coordinated approach to reintegration based on international best practices.

The selected Sustainable Development Goals create a logically connected block that covers basic infrastructure (water, energy), socio-economic aspects (labor, employment, community development) and institutional-spatial vector (urban planning, sustainability, innovation). Their implementation provides a minimal but vital foundation for the reintegration of territories that have been under the control of foreign authorities for years, losing ties with the Ukrainian socio-economic space.

At the same time, these Goals can become a reference point for the formation of state policy on post-conflict development, international assistance and resource mobilization - both within the country and at the level of international donors. In the future, based on this priority core, there may be a gradual expansion to other Sustainable Development Goals, such as quality education, gender equality or partnerships (more in table 3).

Table 3.

SDGs priority matrix in the reintegration of TOT Ukraine

SDG	Bakhmut	Melitopol	Sevastopol
SDG 6: Clean water and adequate sanitation.	Marine ecosystem under pressure depletion of water resources		
SDG 7: Affordable and clean energy	Focus on diversity and independence		
SDG 8: Decent work and economic growth	reorientation from the military-industrial focus		
SDG 9: Industrialization, innovation and infrastructure	Rethinking the role of the city		
SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities	political integration, Ukrainization		
SDG 11: Sustainable development of cities and communities	subordination to the logistics of the Bakhchisarai district, change in social status		
SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production	Focus on cycling economy, and sustainable logistics		
SDG 13: Climate Action.	Maritime policy and decarbonization of the fleet		
SDG 16: Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions.	reintegration, deconstruction of the Russian narrative		
SDG 17: Partnerships for the Goals	Geopolitical sensitivity		

- *The highest priority - core SDG for the territory*
- *High priority – critical to recovery, impacts safety, dignity, infrastructure.*
- *Medium priority – important, but implementation depends on basic stabilization.*
- *Moderate priority – strategically significant, but deferred or secondary to basic needs.*

Source: Developed by authors based on [22; 23]

Summarizing the results of the analysis, it can be stated that the reintegration of the temporarily occupied territories of Ukraine requires a multi-vector approach based on the principles of sustainable development. The conducted PESTEL analysis shows that political challenges, legal uncertainty, economic degradation, social fragmentation, environmental risks and technological barriers require a comprehensive response. At the same time, the identified priority Sustainable Development Goals – including ensuring access to water, energy, decent work, infrastructure restoration, reducing inequalities, strengthening institutions and climate adaptation – form a logical framework for planning actions in the reconstruction process. Systematic consideration of these priorities will allow not only to restore territories after occupation, but also to build resilient communities capable of developing in the face of global challenges. The Ukrainian experience can become an example of the integration of SDGs in a complex post-conflict context and confirmation of the effectiveness of global goals in national transformation.

Conclusions. Summing up, there are two major scenarios. The diplomatic scenario provides an opportunity to preserve and repurpose capacities for the needs of Ukraine and peaceful life. The diplomatic scenario provides for more favorable conditions for the development of infrastructure and basic social functions of the state.

Another scenario, the military one, provides for greater risks of destruction of critical infrastructure facilities and, accordingly, more complex options for implementing the SR Goals. The military scenario, in essence, provides for the restoration of destroyed facilities and their improvement during post-war measures. It was found that more than 40 critical infrastructure facilities in Crimea could, under the conditions of the military de-occupation scenario, create a sanitary and communal crisis that would threaten basic life needs.

In conclusion, we note that the reintegration potential (according to two basic scenarios - minor destruction during the de-occupation process and significant destruction):

1. Infrastructure. According to our estimates, it can be used for the development of the territory. Significant damage is unlikely.

2. Industrial. The potential for internal economic growth and meeting domestic needs will be preserved. Most of the real sector of the Crimean economy has military or paramilitary significance and this will require significant transformations. The food industry and the agro-industrial sector will be preserved as much as possible and adapted to the Ukrainian regulatory field.

3. Agriculture. The level of adaptation is currently maximum, because it consists mainly of small and medium-sized farmers and the processing of local raw materials.

4. Logistics. It will change dramatically due to the reorientation of transport flows; however, part of the rolling stock will remain. In an extremely negative scenario, the rolling stock may be significantly damaged.

5. Public services, education, healthcare, etc. It will require significant state control and management. Special role of the Military Administration and Military-Civil Administrations on the ground.

For effective reintegration of the Crimean economy, it is necessary:

Expert work on developing strategies and plans for their implementation (available documents do not meet current requirements)

The presence of a single central executive body for the implementation of the reintegration policy, the potential of the existing central executive bodies is insufficient (Ministry for the Reintegration of the Temporarily Occupied Territories of Ukraine)

Formation of an effective personnel reserve and involvement of material and organizational efforts of our partners for the implementation of the reintegration policy (especially for the middle level of management and top management). For example, the need for secondary education workers alone, provided that the current legislation on collaborationism remains unchanged, is 20,000 people.

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